

RIS-aided Multi-hop Backhauling for 5G/6G UAV-assisted Access Points

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Outline

1. Motivation and considered scenario
2. Problem formulation
3. Solution
4. Results
5. Conclusion

Motivation

- Ultra dense networks is one of the key cases for 5G and beyond
- How to backhaul?
- mmWave through LOS
- RISs can overcome LOS blocking
- Drone base stations for temporary throughput boosts or disaster scenarios

RIS and drone relay stations providing backhaul connectivity to a small cell

Considered Scenario

- Problem: establishing backhaul connectivity between two cells in urban environment
- Backhaul hops using RISs or drone relay stations

Multi-hop relaying between macro base station and a small cell

Selection of hops

Constraints

- $P_n^R \geq P_{min}$
- Clear LOS

Goals

- Minimizing number of hops (least DRS possible)
- Minimizing path loss
- Reducing latency, energy consumption

Solution

Finding LOS feasibility

Input: set of obstacles, possible locations

Output: for any two points, is the LOS path clear?

The results is a visibility graph $G_v = (V, E_v)$

V : set of vertices (possible locations)

E_v : set of edges indicating LOS

Finding path with least cost

Input: modified G'_v , source, and destination

Output: selected hops

Using a shortest path algorithm on a weighted graph (e.g., Dijkstra's algorithm)

Setting costs to edges and RIS-related modifications

Solution

Finding LOS feasibility

- Given obstacles graph $G(V, E)$
- Lee's visibility graph algorithm [D. Lee, Proximity and Reachability in the Plane. University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, 1978.]

Example from robot motion planning

Solution

Graph preprocessing

- Add new edges between all points covered by RIS (virtual LOS)
- Find path loss, PL , of each edge
- Remove edges that don't satisfy

$$P_n^R \geq P_{min}$$

- Edge cost is defined as

$$D = \begin{cases} \overline{PL}_{direct} + P & \text{if direct edge,} \\ \overline{PL}_{RIS} + P & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Path loss values are normalized, and P is penalty per hop

Visibility of single RIS

Solution

Shortest path selection

- Applying Dijkstra's algorithm results in finding successive hops with clear LOS
- Path loss and number of hops are minimized

Selected shortest path example

Simulation

Number of points requiring N hops

- Less hops translates to:
 1. Reduced latency and
 2. Reduced energy consumption

Number of points

Simulation

Number of reachable locations with 2 hops

- Without RISs: 122 locations are reachable
- With RIS: 255

Locations reachable with a maximum of 2 hops

Simulation

Number of reachable locations with 3 hops

- Without RISs: 392 locations are reachable
- With RIS: 541

Locations reachable with a maximum of 3 hops

Conclusion

- Algorithm for finding backhaul hops with or without RIS
- Advantage of deploying RIS (reachability, latency, energy consumption)
- Future work
 - Selection of small cells locations to maximize throughput
 - Optimizing RIS location
 - More detailed RIS modeling